

Trip Report: Pebble Beach, Red River Gorge

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June 2021

Synopsis

Discovery of confirmatory sandstone “stratification” that eliminates (by circumstance) the uniformitarian pathway of Devonian “coral reef” formation in the Daniel Boone National Forest leyline. On site discovery at the Red River Gorge, an exact matching formation (clearly electrically formed) to Dogfoot Hollow, also in the DBNF leyline. However, the two sites are not along similar fault lines or in the same vicinity, precluded the already impossible upthrust, unupthrust, re-upthrust to same angle, and reversal of this, all millions of years apart. Figures shown were taken by the author on separate AKHA field trips. Angle measurements included are from current perspectives.

The author not being a geologist can make no final determinations, except to statistically preclude impossible uniformitarian solutions.

Included is a comparison of an unusual, also impossible to explain by uniformitarian methods, stone from a similar Devonian shelf, located at Garden of the Gods, IL, which has the same type of liesegang banding, albeit more severe, with a generally unremarked about astrobleme, suggesting a possible bolide+electrical explosion event. Unlike the Big Sink Peratt thunderbolt strike site, GotG is definitely on the bowshock edge of a bolide strike, however, the banding suggests rapid changes in stone morphology. The photo included, however, suggests polar reconfiguration through charge separation.

Figures

Figure 1 - Layered “stratification” in sandstone morphology with clear changes to angles, location: pebble beach, Red River Gorge, 37.85868, -83.67024. Photo taken 6/26/2021; credit: author

Figure 2 - Same effect located 60km away at "Dogfoot Hollow, again with sandstone morphology, location: 37.53264,-84.21768, photo taken 11/10/2018; credit: author

Figure 3 - Dogfoot Hollow "Mayan Head"; Figure 4 - Dogfoot Hollow "manatee" figurine; credit: L. Pennington¹

Figure 5 - pendant made by owner of piece that was clearly originally a pendant of the Cosmic Face motif

Author expects dating to be late Megalithic to Transition Period. (1500 BCE-500 BCE)

¹ These items are owned by an undisclosed party which discovered them at the culvert waterfall at DH; they were loaned to the author who took them to AKHA, where Lee photographed them, and subsequently returned. The purpose of the trip on 11/10/18 was to search for evidence of a larger native involvement because of the proximity to Indianfort and Pilot Knob, and there were excellent proofs of fortification, but no new figurines were found. A future trip has yet to be planned.

Figure 6 - Distance calculated via KY From Above: 59.1-60.5 km; credit: KYFromAbove, Google Maps, and Author (hiddendestinationsky.com)²

Remarks

Pebble Beach is a rock climbing destination, and it was sheerly by accident the author came across this confirmatory piece of data. The angle changes go from 0 to roughly 15 degrees, back to 0, back to 15, and then back to 0 again, over a period the author approximates to be nearly a 500 million years total (unless the site is electrically formed). What isn't clear is that it is impossible for the land to have tilted, and returned, and re-tilted, and returned if under the electrical influence of another star. However, the likelihood of this is, to the author, lower than an electrical formation probability. What is certainly impossible is a purely upthrust/downthrust vector hypothesis, especially given the repeated cyclical nature of the stratification, angles, etc.

Please note the Dogfoot Hollow site repeats the situation 3 times, and so the author hypothesizes that there is a 3rd set below the dirt at Pebble Beach, not yet revealed, as the reader will note the first layer seen is already on an angle.

A complete type up of the visit can be found in the AKHA journal publication, or in summary of Ramon's articles there.³ Several more potentially electrical images are in that article.

² As can be seen the locations are also on opposite sides of the leyline, albeit at energetic peaks (Pinnacles/Pilot Knob region) near to Zion Mountain, and Red River Gorge, which has a lot of fluvial activity due to increased rainfall in the area.

³ <https://bit.ly/3h1ztBe>, pp28-35

Garden of the Gods

For context, the author visited the Garden of the Gods purely out of interest in the liesegang bands, and not on behalf of the AKHA or to do EPEMC research. He did not know the site exists on the rim of an astrobleme for another 2 years. The following figures will demonstrate.

Figure 7 - Shawnee National Forest “Hicks Dome” astrobleme⁴; credit: Google Earth/Maps

⁴ “Hicks Dome Location: southern Illinois, 15 miles southeast of Harrisburg Type: faulted dome formed by intrusive and explosive igneous activity Diameter: 8 miles 22 Age: Early Permian (about 270 million years ago) Description: Rampino and Volk (1996) listed this as one of eight aligned impact craters, but geologists who have looked closely at Hicks Dome agree on its igneous origin. Although complexly faulted, the structure is basically **a dome lacking the ring depression and raised rim** of a complex impact crater. **No shock indicators exist.** Ultramafic dikes, sills, and plugs along with intrusive breccias radiate from the apex along a NW-SE axis. There is **no gravity anomaly; a magnetic high is centered 6 miles northeast.** Seismic reflection profiles indicate that doming extends into Precambrian crystalline rocks at a depth of greater than 2 miles. Potassium-argon dating of biotite and hornblende from intrusive rocks yields Early Permian age. Hicks Dome lies at the center of a mineralized region, the Illinois-Kentucky fluorspar district. Potter et al. (1995) interpreted origin by a combination of magma intrusion and explosive brecciation within Precambrian basement. References: Bradburn and Baxter, 1992; Potter et al., 1995.”

Figure 8 - Heavy liesegang banding, precluding the possibility of untouched morphology through stratification; credit: author 8/5/19⁵

http://library.isgs.illinois.edu/Pubs/pdfs/Manuscripts/External/MS_Nelson_WJ_15.pdf

Respectfully the author must disagree with large portions of this, and yet the bolded area invites more thought.

⁵ The entire album is full of even more ridiculous examples that violate uniformitarian principles. Besides of which the proximity to a known catastrophic location precludes typical Devonian “seabed” stratification as a vector, whatever the authors of the park signs may wish to teach the public!

Figure 9 - Polarized liesegang banding, with impossible vein removal along similar vector⁶; credit: author

⁶ Please note the geologist claim that the iron is eroded from the upper new layer (by oxidation) is impossible if the older, longer exposed region retains the banding. The claim is the bands remain because sandstone is less durable, in which case then the upper sandstone layers should be what is removed! Besides of which the sudden morphology shift is unmistakable. The author would ask a professional geologist to review the data themselves!

Conclusions

The sites above are just a small handful of examples of electrical geological sites. In 2019, the author's friend and colleague published a piece on the formation of the Upheaval Dome in Utah⁷, and asked this author to help with edits. The evidence of many sites, including the Big Sink⁸, Pilot Knob(s), and various large formations such as Stone Mountain, Ayer's Rock, Shiprock, Candlestick Knobs, Devil's Tower, and much else is mounting. What these sites need is a more thorough investigation. While it is obvious to those who understand electricity that the Knobs region of Kentucky (not in the DBNF leyline!) is a lichtenburg, it is not obvious to your average geologist, who must resort to improbable and even impossible uniformitarian theories to force-fit the data. However, the above data preclude and constrain such theories, resulting in a need to "return to formula." More data collection is needed, as well as lab examples (such as Billy Yelverton's lab), for the data to be

considered ultimately conclusive, however. Therefore the only conclusions in this trip report are that the geologists are wrong, but so far no one is 100% right. Therefore the author requests assistance from the geological community in these matters, and for this to be an open dialogue.

Figure 10 - "soda" veins at Dogfoot Hollow, not found elsewhere on site, stone looking charred and destructed by high heat process (similar elevation to the other layers); credit: author.

⁷ [http://www.iiisci.org/journal/CV\\$/sci/pdfs/ZA014LF20r.pdf](http://www.iiisci.org/journal/CV$/sci/pdfs/ZA014LF20r.pdf)

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https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332831733_Proposed_Discovery_of_Perattian_Thunderbolt_of_the_Gods_Strike_Location_in_Versailles_KY_Comparison_of_Predicted_Models_and_LiDAR_scans_of_Big_Sink_location_in_Woodford_County_Addendum_for_Plasmaglyph